

Deliverable D5.1: Climate risk assessment of the European financial system against global climate physical risks

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Description:

D5.1 provides a quantitative assessment of climate physical risks cascading through the financial system for European investors. The physical component of climate-related financial risk, intended both as chronic and acute impacts, has attracted the attention of scholars and practitioners. Nevertheless, science-based and transparent solutions to assess and price cascading climate physical risks are still missing. This represents a main gap for climate risk assessment, and thus an obstacle to investment and policy decisions.

To fill this gap, we develop a methodology to assess the asset-level climate physical risks and the cascading financial losses for European investors. We first introduce the concept of cascading climate physical risks for business and finance, meaning the losses that could propagate from the affected assets through the economy and end up affecting investors. Second, we qualitatively identify the risk transmission channels from climate physical risks to the agents and sectors of the economy, private and public finance, discussing the direct, indirect and cascading impacts. Third, we describe the methodological framework that we developed to assess cascading climate risks to business and finance. As a main innovation on the state-of-the-art, our methodology applies at the asset-level (productive plants) and covers the steps to compute how climate physical risks translate into firms' performance, economic losses and financial risks for the investors.

We then apply the methodology to global physical assets that are exposed to tropical cyclones. Such assets are owned by publicly listed companies headquartered outside of the European Union, and that issued stocks which are owned by European financial actors.

We find that the combination of tail acute climate risks from hurricanes with chronic risks can lead up to 11.85% increase in estimated investors' portfolio losses, in

comparison to an estimate conducted without taking tail climate risks into account. Moreover, we find that climate physical risks can cascade on the European financial system.

This work benefitted from the collaboration and inputs of the ETH team (WP2), the CMCC team (WP3) and the ECDPM team (WP5).

Version 1

Delivery Date: 19.10.2022

This project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 821010.

Document information	
Responsible Person and Affiliation	Irene Monasterolo, EDHEC Business School, ERCII/ WU
Due Date / Delivery Date	19.10.2022
State	Final draft
Reviewers	Christopher Reyer
Version	1.0
Confidentiality	PU
Suggested citation	Monasterolo, I., Bressan, G., Duranovic, A., Auer, C., Bilal, B., Bosello, F., Delpiazzi, E., Kropf, C. M., and Parrado, R. (2022). Deliverable D5.1: Climate risk assessment of the European financial system against global climate physical risks. Deliverable of the H2020 CASCADES project (Cascading climate risks: Towards adaptive and resilient European Societies), 47 pp.

Climate risk assessment of the European financial system against global climate physical risks

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Data	9
2.1 Equity data	10
2.2 Business-lines and company-level data	12
2.3 Asset-level data	13
2.4 Bank data	14
3. Scenario selection	15
4. Model	19
4.1 Methodological framework	19
4.2 Acute risks	20
4.3 Chronic risks	23
4.4 Climate financial valuation	25
4.5 Interbank network model	28
5. Results	30
5.1 Acute vs chronic shocks at the asset and firm level	30
5.2 Acute shocks lead to large losses on firms' equity value	31
5.3 Distribution of firms' losses by sectors and countries	33
5.4 Portfolio tail losses from acute physical shocks	38
5.5 Financial interconnectedness and leverage can amplify climate-related losses	39
6. Conclusions	40
7. References	42

1. Introduction

The exposure of financial actors (e.g. banks, insurance firms, pension funds, investment funds) to direct physical risks from natural climate hazards can be geographically confined and localized to a specific country or region. Consider, for example, the case of home insurance or a regional bank that lends to local firms. However, financial risks triggered by climate change can become transboundary because of the global nature of investments (Carter et al., 2021) meaning that they can affect investors that are located far away from the initial impact of a climate-related hazard¹ (Bressan et al., 2022).

The analysis of climate physical risks, defined as the risk stemming from either climate-related hazards (acute risk, e.g. Beirne et al., 2021; Caloia and Jansen, 2021; Dunz et al., 2021; Mandel et al., 2021) or long-run climate impacts (chronic risk, see e.g. Dietz et al., 2016) on the economy and the financial system has received growing attention. Nevertheless, climate physical risk assessment faces several methodological and conceptual challenges in terms of asset-level data, the relevance and use of scenarios (Ranger et al., 2022), the financial valuation of physical risks, and risk assessment for investors (Fiedler et al., 2021). Addressing these gaps is crucial to inform the reallocation of capital into activities that contribute to adapt and build resilience to climate change (Kreibiehl et al., 2022), and to design tailored policies and financial instruments.

Many international initiatives (e.g. UN NetZero Assets Owners Alliance² and the Science Based Targets Initiative³), consulting firms and major data providers (e.g. BloombergNEF⁴, Refinitiv Eikon⁵, S&P Global Trucost⁶), as well as financial institutions for development (Ahairwe et al., 2022) have also recognized the importance of disclosing and assessing climate-related financial risks. Potential lack of insurance and hedging products, as well as the lack of systematic adaptation plans and their implementation also influence a growing investors' consideration of climate risks. Indeed, losses from a climate hazard that hits a firm's productive plants and economic activities in one geographic area could cascade across value chains (Benzie and Persson, 2019; Carter et al., 2021; West et al., 2021), and materialize in the portfolio of an investor located far away from the original disaster.

In Figure 1, we qualitatively illustrate how acute climate physical risks (e.g., hurricanes) hitting non-EU regions could cascade to the European business and financial sectors. For instance, hurricanes can damage physical assets and destroy capital stock of firms, thus decreasing their profitability and increasing their probability of default. On the one hand, lower profitability may lead firms to decrease

¹ Defined as the potential occurrence of climate-related physical events or trends that may cause damage and loss.

² <https://www.unepfi.org/net-zero-alliance/>

³ <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/>

⁴ <https://about.bnef.com/>

⁵ <https://www.refinitiv.com/en/products/eikon-trading-software>

⁶ <https://www.spglobal.com/esg/trucost>

investments and start laying off workers, thus negatively affecting consumption, economic growth, and government’s fiscal revenues. Lower GDP growth and fiscal revenues, and high reconstruction costs, can then lead to higher debt/GDP ratio and higher costs of sovereign financing on the market, potentially affecting sovereign financial stability. While acute climate physical risks such as hurricanes are not a new phenomenon, and some degree of adaptation to them exists, their patterns are changing as a consequence of climate change. Thus, the overall risk is changing, and so the potential cascading dynamics.

On the other hand, if the affected firms have financed themselves by issuing securities (e.g. stocks or bonds), an increase in the default probability of the issuer implies a decrease in the expected value of the securities. This, in turn, could lead to losses for the portfolio of European financial institutions that own such securities. Furthermore, financial losses could cascade from the portfolio of one investor to other investors through their holdings of financial contracts and securities. Such losses could be amplified through reverberation in the financial network, with potential implications on financial stability at the level of individual institutions, and for the global financial system (Battiston et al., 2012).

Figure 1: Cascading risks from climate hazards (hurricanes) hitting non-EU regions. Climate hazards damage physical assets and destroy capital stock of firms issuing financial contracts, thus decreasing their profitability and increasing their probability of default. The increase in default probability of issuers implies a decrease in expected value of the financial contracts they have issued, and thus a negative shock on the portfolio of European financial institutions. Deterioration of credit worthiness of impacted firms leads to an increase in their capital cost, which can, in turn, hinder their recovery, and further aggravate the losses. Moreover, if European financial institutions are also exposed to public sector debt of a region hit by a climate disaster, they can suffer further portfolio losses because, inter alia, lower operating earnings of firms decrease real GDP via lower corporate taxes, thus widening government deficit and hampering sovereign’s ability to repay. Source: adapted from Dunz et al. (2021).

Currently, four knowledge gaps limit the assessment of climate physical risks and their potential cascading losses in the economy and finance.

First, despite the progress being made in spatial finance⁷, there is still limited access to data, in particular at plant level (Caldecott et al., 2018; Eberenz et al., 2020). Poor availability and access to data may lead to an incorrect estimation of climate-related economic and financial shocks because the geographical location and type of activity are key drivers of exposure to physical risk. Most databases provide highly aggregated information on socio-economic losses (e.g. country-level, see EMDAT: EMDAT CRED / UCLouvain, 2009). When disaggregated information about loss type is available, it is often not comparable across countries (e.g. DesInventar⁸) or it is proprietary, preventing an understanding of drivers of results, and the replicability of the analysis (Cormack, 2020; Li and Gallagher, 2022).

Second, reconstructing the ownership chains from plants to firms and investors is a challenge, due to the complexity of the global ownership network (Garcia-Bernardo et al., 2017; Vitali et al., 2011). For investors, data availability across major asset classes varies. Commercial data providers such as Orbis⁹ or Refinitiv Eikon offer data of equity holdings for individual financial institutions and have been used for climate stress tests (see e.g. Battiston et al., 2017), as well as syndicated loans data,¹⁰ used, for example, in Bateson and Saccardi (2021). Real estate data can be obtained in a similar way, for example from Moody's Analytics¹¹ mortgage dataset (Calabrese et al. 2021). Banking book loans are not disclosed beyond aggregate levels. Moreover, these data are just a fixed-time snapshot at time of collection and may differ from what is held on balance sheets (Bateson and Saccardi, 2021).

Third, the lack of a comprehensive approach to scenario analysis for climate physical risk limits their relevance for climate-financial risk assessment (Ranger et al. 2022), e.g. in the context of IPCC (2021) and NGFS (2022). Current analyses of physical risks either rely on scenarios of chronic risks, i.e. long-term shifts in climate patterns such as sea-level rise or chronic heat waves (e.g. from the Intersectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project – ISIMIP¹²), or on acute risks, i.e. event-driven risks including increased severity of extreme weather events such as cyclones (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019), droughts or floods. There seem to be a dichotomy between “climate impact modelling” (with a focus on climate hence longer-term effects) and probabilistic disaster risk assessment (with a focus on explicit events). This in turn affect the ability of modellers to translate the biophysical impacts into socioeconomic and human impacts through damage functions, leading to an underestimation of the economic shocks and their financial impacts.

⁷ Spatial finance is intended as “the integration of geospatial data and analysis into financial theory and practice”, (<https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/>).

⁸ <https://www.desinventar.net/>

⁹ <https://www.bvdinfo.com/en-gb/>

¹⁰ <https://www.loanconnector.com/>

¹¹ <https://www.moodyanalytics.com/>

¹² <https://www.isimip.org/>

The fourth gap stands in the translation of economic losses into shocks on prices (Giglio et al., 2021) to support corporate disclosure (Capasso et al., 2020) and portfolio risk management. Valuation models that adjust growth levels according to estimates of impact of climate-hazards and scenarios are still missing. Nevertheless, in the context of climate change, assuming all companies will converge to a unique long-run growth rate (Birman et al., 2015) could be misleading and lead to an underestimation of risk.

In Bressan et al. (2022), we proposed a methodological framework for a dynamic, asset-level assessment of climate physical risks, considering the cascading economic and financial losses through the ownership chains. In this deliverable, we employ the methodology from Bressan et al. (2022) to assess the exposure of European investors to non-EU physical risks. To do so, we collect a database of equity investments from European financial actors into non-EU firms. We also collect information on the global distribution of assets owned by these firms. We perform a climate-adjusted financial valuation of the equity contracts considering asset level losses. Finally, we assess the systemic financial implications of cascading climate physical risks for the EU financial sector.

We find that acute risks from tropical cyclones can significantly affect companies' assets and thus their equity value. In this context, climate tail risk (Weitzman, 2009) is particularly important for climate-related hazards. In this paper, we define climate tail risk as the larger damages to assets stemming from extreme events.

Our results show that, at the portfolio level, neglecting tail acute risks can lead to significant underestimations of risk measures, e.g. Expected Shortfall (up to 11.85% underestimation of portfolio losses).

Moreover, we study the implications for financial stability of cascading physical risks. To the direct shocks from physical risks on equity portfolios, we add the analysis of the indirect shocks emerging from the revaluation of financial contracts within the banking network. We find that significant losses may emerge in the system and that the most impacted banks could suffer losses on Common Equity Tier 1 (CET1)¹³ (BCBS, 2010) capital up to 2% circa. While the results may appear contained, it is important to consider that financial institutions tend to be highly leveraged, i.e. to have small capital compared to total assets. Thus, even small losses on CET1 capital can trigger instability for individual banks and systemic risk.

The document is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the climate, financial and non-financial data used. Section 3 presents and discusses the combination of SSPs-RCPs scenarios used. Section 4 illustrates the methodological framework while section 5 presents the results. Section 6 concludes.

¹³ "Common Equity Tier 1 capital (CET1) is the highest quality of regulatory capital, as it absorbs losses immediately when they occur." (BCBS, 2019: p. 1/2).

2. Data

To assess climate financial risk of the European financial system from global climate physical risks, we first collect information on investments of the European financial actors in publicly listed companies headquartered in non-EU countries. We focus on equity shares as a financial contract. The choice of financial instrument type is determined by data availability. At the level of individual financial institutions, the information about equity holdings in publicly listed companies is publicly available from commercial data providers (e.g. Refinitiv Eikon). On the other hand, data on bond holdings and banking book loans is usually proprietary and, thus, cannot be easily obtained on the global scale.

Second, we develop a database model to collect and logically connect information about the firms that issued these equity shares and of the individual physical assets owned by them. The database model provides a granular and comprehensive overview of the climate, financial and non-financial characteristics of companies, collecting information on their productive assets, location, type of activity, prices, etc.

Third, we disaggregate company-level information by asset and geography, considering the company as a portfolio of geographically distributed assets (Pidun, 2019). This approach allows us to downscale climate risk assessment to the fundamental business units of the firm, considering their potentially different exposure to climate-related hazards, due to the geographical location of the productive assets. At the same time, we consider issues related to workers and crops' productivity via the macro-economic model. To do so, we first collect data on companies main operating activity, leveraging the NACE Rev.2 classification¹⁴.

Then, we consolidate a database of physical assets using information retrieved from different data providers¹⁵. For each asset, we retrieve or estimate a location, production capacity, monetary value, useful residual life, technology, operating status and ownership. Since available asset level information does not cover all asset types, our analysis, although global, covers only a selection of asset types. For example, power plants are covered but chemical factories are not. For more details on the covered asset types, see Subsection 2.3.

Finally, we collect balance-sheet data, i.e. data from financial statements on assets, liabilities and equity, for European banks to assess the impacts of physical risks on financial stability.

The following subsections provide a description of the data sources.

¹⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/ks-ra-07-015>

¹⁵ For instance, Refinitiv Eikon (<https://eikon.thomsonreuters.com/index.html>), and S&P (<https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/>).

2.1 Equity data

We extract the dataset of exposures via equity contracts to non-EU publicly listed companies of European financial actors, as of June 2020 from the Ownership Universe in Refinitiv Eikon Screener App. We consider all European financial actors headquartered in the EU¹⁶. In addition, we consider financial actors from the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) Member States¹⁷, European microstates¹⁸, the United Kingdom (GB), together with its Crown dependencies¹⁹, and all the Overseas Territories²⁰ of the countries mentioned. Whenever the data on the country of headquarters (HQ) of an investor are not available, we use the country of incorporation. Furthermore, we consolidate investors at the level of ultimate parent. For the consolidation of investors, we apply the methodology used by Refinitiv Eikon and assign consolidated investor if the direct or indirect ownership interest exceeds 50%. However, whenever the consolidated investor is a sovereign, a foundation, or a corporate entity domiciled outside of European countries considered, we assign the European financial institution closest to the investor's ultimate parent on the ownership pathway as consolidated investor.

The original dataset retrieved from Refinitiv Eikon contains around 1 million individual equity holdings. However, that dataset also includes equity holdings in EU-headquartered companies and equity holdings of individuals, non-financial corporations (NFC), foundations, and governments. Our analysis focuses on non-EU²¹ equity holdings of European financial institutions, so we remove all the equity holdings in EU companies and all the shareholders which are non-financial actors from the dataset.

We consolidate individual public companies' ownership at the level of investor parents. In terms of financial instruments, we consider ordinary shares and American Depositary Receipts (ADRs)^{22,23}. The financial actors' equity exposures to these two types of financial contracts account for almost 90% of the total value of equity exposures held by financial institutions in the dataset. The final dataset contains

¹⁶ Austria (AT), Belgium (BE), Bulgaria (BG), Croatia (HR), Cyprus (CY), Czechia (CZ), Denmark (DK), Estonia (EE), Finland (FI), France (FR), Germany (DE), Greece (GR), Hungary (HU), Ireland (IE), Italy (IT), Latvia (LV), Lithuania (LT), Luxembourg (LU), Malta (MT), Netherlands (NL), Poland (PL), Portugal (PT), Romania (RO), Slovakia (SK), Slovenia (SI), Spain (ES), and Sweden (SE).

¹⁷ Iceland (IS), Liechtenstein (LI), Norway (NO), and Switzerland (CH).

¹⁸ Andorra (AD) and Monaco (MC).

¹⁹ Guernsey (GG), the Isle of Man (IM), and Jersey (JE).

²⁰ Anguilla (AI), Bermuda (BM), British Virgin Islands (VG), Cayman Islands (KY), Curacao (CW), Gibraltar (GI), and Greenland (GL).

²¹ Here, we consider all the publicly listed companies with headquarters outside the European Union or its member states' overseas territories.

²² We consider ordinary shares (including both fully- and partly-paid ordinary shares) and American depository receipts (ADR) because a similar equity valuation approach can be applied to these financial instruments.

²³ Characteristics of equity securities held by a given investor are the following: security identifiers - Reuters Instrument Code (RIC) and International Securities Identification Number (ISIN); type of security; filing date and filing type; and holdings value in USD.

479,690 individual equity holdings of 2,804 European consolidated²⁴ investors that are exposed to 17,659 non-EU publicly listed companies (i.e. issuers of equity^{25,26}). The equity issuers are headquartered in 93 countries and own physical assets all over the world. The largest number of equity issuers is headquartered in the United States (3,548), Japan (2,640), China (1,498), United Kingdom (1,424), South Korea (1,117), Taiwan (917), and India (823). The total value of equity exposures of European investors to non-EU companies in our dataset amounts to 5.43 trillion USD.

Finally, by building on the climate stress-test methodology developed in Battiston et al. (2017), we group consolidated investors into five investor types (i.e. Banks, Insurance and pension funds, Investment funds, Other credit institutions, and Other financial services), based on their NACE Rev.2 4-digit codes. For each consolidated investor type, Table 1 reports the number and the value (in trillion USD) of individual equity holdings. The consolidated investors with the largest equity exposures are Norges Bank (617.63 billion USD), Blackrock Group Ltd (475.77 billion USD), Legal & General Group PLC (218.14 billion USD), UBS Group AG (156.37 billion USD), and Janus Henderson Group PLC (155.49 billion USD).

Consolidated investor type	NACE Rev.2 4-digit codes	Number of consolidated investors with a given type	Percentage of consolidated investors with a given type (%)	Number of individual equity holdings by investor type	Value of equity holdings by investor type (trillion USD)
Banks	K.64.1	239	8.52	148,754	1.61
Insurance and pension funds (IPFs)	K.65.1- K.65.3, K.66.2	137	4.89	56,444	0.46
Investment funds (IFs)	K.64.2, K.64.3, K.64.9.1, K.66.1.2, K.66.3	1,446	51.57	206,842	2.74
Other credit institutions (OCIs)	K.64.9.2, K.64.9.9	580	20.68	49,246	0.41
Other financial services (OFSs)	K.66.1.1, K.66.1.9	402	14.34	18,404	0.22
Total	K.64-66	2,804	100	479,690	5.44

Table 1: Classification of consolidated investors into types based on their NACE Rev.2 4-digit codes. This table reports the number and relative share of consolidated investors, and the number and value (in trillion USD) of individual equity holdings, for each consolidated investor type. Retrieved from: Refinitiv Eikon. Source: adapted from Battiston et al. (2017).

²⁴ Investors' characteristics are the following: investor name; Refinitiv PermID; Legal Entity Identifier (LEI); country of HQ; country of incorporation; NACE Rev.2 class (i.e., 4-digit code); and NACE Rev.2 section; and consolidated investor name; Refinitiv PermID; Legal Entity Identifier (LEI); country of HQ; country of incorporation; NACE Rev.2 class (i.e., 4-digit code); and NACE Rev.2 section.

²⁵ Characteristics of equity securities' issuers are the following: company name; Refinitiv PermID; Legal Entity Identifier (LEI); country of HQ; NACE Rev.2 class (i.e., 4-digit code); and NACE Rev.2 section.

²⁶ <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/solutions/sp-capital-ig-pro>

2.2 Business-lines and company-level data

Different industries will suffer heterogeneous impacts from climate physical risks, as highlighted e.g. in Delpiazzo et al. (2021). Thus, as many companies are involved in multiple industries, they should be analysed as a portfolio of business lines. For example, the South Korean conglomerate SK Networks Co., Ltd is involved in multiple businesses including ICT distribution, automotive services (such as maintenance, tire distribution, car parts exports), petrochemicals, hotels, rental of cars and home appliances. Depending on the climate change scenario, these businesses will be heterogeneously impacted (see also Delpiazzo et al., 2021). Considering the company as being involved in only one of these businesses implies a significant information loss. For instance, the company's most important segment for revenues is ICT distribution, but this segment covers only 47%²⁷ of the company's revenues. Thus, considering the company as an ICT distributor, rather than a conglomerate involved in multiple businesses, implies an information loss on 53% of the company's revenues.

The process of extracting revenue shares for each firm's business line is labour intensive and time consuming. While machine learning techniques can help in principle, they have not yet been applied to this problem. Thus, it is not possible for this study to explicitly distinguish companies' revenue shares by business line. For this reason, we adopt the assumption that one company is involved in only one business line, being its main one, as identified by its NACE 4-digit code. Where applicable, manual reclassification is applied as explained below.

For example, the company Shell PLC would normally be involved in multiple business lines such as oil extraction, gas extraction, chemicals, electricity generation. But for the purposes of this deliverable, it will be considered as an oil company only. Note that even this level of detail cannot always be inferred from NACE 4-digit codes: in the electricity sector, for example, it is not possible to classify issuers across the four activities used in Delpiazzo et al. (2021), namely Electricity-Fossil, Electricity-Hydro, Electricity-Renewable, and Electricity-Nuclear. This is because the only electricity generation code in the NACE Rev.2 classification is D.35.11, which does not distinguish by energy source.

Thus, we manually reclassify electricity companies using the following procedure: (i) for all companies, we gather the list of electricity generating assets (see also Section 2.3) and compute the total share of generating capacity across the four activities (fossil, hydro, renewable, nuclear); (ii) we also gather the business description and the percentage of renewable energy generation from Refinitiv Eikon; (iii) we assign issuers to the business line that has the highest share of capacity. For example, RWE AG is mostly operating fossil assets and, thus, we assign it to the Electricity-Fossil sector, while Falck Renewables Spa is mostly operating renewable assets and, thus, we assign it to the Electricity-Renewables sector.

²⁷ As of 2021. Source: authors' elaboration, based on SK Networks Co., Ltd annual report, available at: https://www.sknetworks.co.kr/upload_skn/investInfo/2021_r_en.pdf

2.3 Asset-level data

In order to attach a geographical dimension to companies' operations, we collect a database of physical assets, which can be subsequently matched to geolocalized information on physical hazards. We collect the information about physical assets of companies from multiple providers, i.e. Refinitiv Eikon, Standard & Poor's Global Market Intelligence²⁸, and the Oxford Spatial Finance Initiative²⁹ (Oxford SFI). For this study, we leverage the following asset types: (i) cement plants (Oxford SFI); (ii) steel plants (Oxford SFI); (iii) mines (S&P); (iv) mining processing facilities (S&P); (v) power plants (S&P); (vi) refineries (Refinitiv Eikon); and (vii) LNG liquefaction and regasification plants (Refinitiv Eikon).

Our combined database of data collected from different providers contains 121,203 assets globally. The most represented assets in the database are power plant units (83,973), followed by mines (34,183), cement facilities (1,277), steel facilities (663), mining processing facilities (473), refineries (388), regasification facilities (126), and liquefaction facilities (120). Figure 2 depicts the global distribution of assets.

Figure 2: Global distribution of assets by type and capacity. Each asset is represented as a dot at the corresponding location defined by its latitude and longitude. The color represents the asset type, such as mine or cement facility. The size of the dot represents the capacity of the asset, where the unit of capacity depends on the asset type (e.g., for cement facilities, the production capacity is expressed in tonnes, for power plants, in MWh, etc.). Retrieved from: Oxford SFI, Refinitiv Eikon, and S&P. Source: authors' own elaboration.

²⁸ <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/>

²⁹ <https://www.cgfi.ac.uk/spatial-finance-initiative/>

Considering the limitations in the availability of asset-level data, we implement a pre-processing pipeline to complete the information retrieved from multiple data providers. The purpose of the pre-processing pipeline is to clean the dataset from irrelevant entries (for example, assets permanently closed, or projects abandoned), and to ensure that all variables relevant for the analysis (e.g. production capacity, coordinates of location, residual life and value) are available for each asset. We use relatively simple but established methodologies to impute capacities, residual lives and values where missing, such as Net Present Value formulas, estimations by cost curves, regressions or regional averages by asset type and/or commodity. While the types of assets in scope are currently limited, the estimation procedures and the database can be easily extended to additional ones.

At the end of the process, the consolidated dataset contains information on geolocalized assets with an estimation of the respective production capacity, monetary value and useful life. It also contains information on technology, operating status and ownership.

Importantly, assets contribute to a specific part of a company's business. For example, a wind farm generates revenues for a company's renewable power business, but hardly for its chemicals business. Thus, we consider assets only when relevant in the equity valuation (see also Subsection 4.4). Since, as mentioned above, each company is assigned only one business line, only one type of assets will be relevant for its equity valuation. Thus, information on some assets will be lost. For example, an electric utility is classified either as renewable, hydroelectric, fossil or nuclear in our study, depending on its most important business line. Nevertheless, a mainly renewable utility can have legacy coal plants still in operation. As the coal plants are not generating revenues for the main business line of the firm, they are disregarded in the equity valuation. Overcoming this limitation will be object of further studies.

2.4 Bank data

While our database of equity positions contains data for all investor types (e.g. banks, investment funds, insurance, etc.), we focus our financial stability analysis on the banking sector because the interbanking network represents a main channel of risk amplification as emerged in the 2008 financial crisis. Thus, our financial stability results shall be considered a lower bound since additional instability dynamics may emerge when considering other financial actors such as investment funds (Roncoroni et al., 2021).

We first extract the list of banks from the initial list of investors. To do so, we start from the dataset of all investors' equity positions as described in section 2.1. We select all unique consolidated investors, leading to a dataset of 2,804 investors³⁰ and we classify them into categories by building on Battiston et al. (2017). The number of

³⁰ We use consolidated investors as we want to assess systemic events on consolidated banks, rather than on their subsidiaries.

investors by category, and the average number of equity positions are reported in Table 1.

Then, we select investors in the categories "Banks" and "Other Credit Institutions" and obtain a total of 819 investors - of which 239 classified as "Banks". Next, we extract from Orbis the list of publicly listed banks in Europe. We match the LEIs from this list to the LEIs of the investors we selected to obtain the entities that are publicly listed banks. Next, we manually screen the results of the matching procedure and add to the sample of public banks those institutions that are not listed but still relevant for the analysis - such as private banks - thus obtaining a list of 271 LEIs. We extract balance sheet variables from Orbis for these companies. The variables describe the asset, the liability and the equity components of the balance sheet.³¹ Furthermore, we remove banks for which data are not complete, leading to a final sample of 149 banks, which we consider in our network model (see Subsection 4.5). The sample covers 70% of the EU largest listed banks and approximately 80% of the EU banking system total assets. These banks hold equity positions in 9,992 unique non-EU companies that populate our equity database.

3. Scenario selection

We conduct our assessment comparing alternative scenarios that focus on two dimensions: (i) future projections of socio-economic conditions - based on Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs), and (ii) future projections of climate - based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). Our starting point is the CASCADDES project deliverable D2.1 (Carter et al., 2020), defining the scenario space for the CASCADDES project (see Figure 3) as combinations of different SSPs and RCPs.

Different RCPs describe the climate dimension, by defining the level of radiative forcing up to 2100, relative to the pre-industrial period. The effects on climate from different levels of radiative forcing are simulated with global climate models. RCPs span the range from 1.9 to 8.5 W/m² (Taylor et al., 2012, Tebaldi et al., 2021). Different SSPs define dimensions of socio-economic conditions relevant for future mitigation of and adaptation to climate change (O'Neill et al., 2017). The degree of international connectivity varies with the different SSPs and plays an important role in the transmission of climate physical risks stemming from non-EU regions. A cross-border perspective of SSPs allows characterizing a wide range of possible future developments regarding the transmission of non-EU climate physical risks. For a

³¹ We extract the following list of variables, both in millions of Euro and in US dollars, for the year 2019 or for the last available year where specified: Operating revenue (Turnover) (for last available year); Number of employees (for last available year); Loans; Gross loans; Less: reserves for impaired loans / NPLs; Other Earning Assets; Loans and advances to banks; of which Reverse Repos, Securities Borrowed and Cash Collaterals; Derivatives (assets); Other securities; Remaining earning assets; Total Earning Assets; Fixed Assets; Non-Earning Assets; Cash & Balances at Central Bank; Goodwill; Other Intangible Assets; Total assets; Deposits & short term funding; Total customer deposits; Deposits from banks; of which Reverse Repos, Securities Borrowed and Cash Collaterals; Other deposits and short-term borrowings; Other interest bearing liabilities; Derivatives (liabilities); Trading liabilities; Long term funding; Other (non-interest bearing); Reserves; Equity; Total liabilities & equity; Tier 1 Ratio (%).

complete discussion on the SSP-RCP architecture see Van Vuuren *et al.* (2014) and Carter et al. (2020).

In terms of finance, international connectivity determines whether and to what extent initial climate-related impacts, triggered by a climate hazard in a non-EU country, can propagate across borders, leading to a shock for financial institutions located in Europe. The degree of international connectivity of financial institutions ranges from low (for regional financial institutions focused on local operations), to high (for global financial institution highly involved in international financial markets). Table 2 reports a detailed overview of the role of finance in SSP narratives.

In SSP1, there is an increasing role of finance in the provision of green investments and financing of adaptation projects in non-EU regions. Cross-country support in the form of development finance initiatives increases financial interconnectedness and leads to a decrease in international inequality. SSP2 is characterized as ‘business as usual’. The financial system is highly interconnected and highly polarized. In contrast to SSP1, climate-driven inequality increases in SSP2 because the level of international financing of adaptation projects remains quite low. SSP3 is a narrative with the lowest level of international interconnectedness. The national focus in this narrative leads to lower levels of external financial exposures, financial de-globalization, and increased financial risk due to a low level of diversification. In SSP4, investment trends around the world differ widely. Finance widens the gap between ‘Global North’ and ‘Global South’, as the access to credit becomes limited and wealth concentration via financial markets increases. Finally, SSP5 is characterized by increased global financial market interconnectedness. However, increased high-carbon investments lead to conditions for amplification of cascading risks stemming from non-EU climate-related hazards.

SSP	Public / private instruments (examples)	Issues at stake for finance
SSP1. Sustainability	Incentives for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects, ODA, hospitals, Green Deal (public); Green and social bonds, ESG funds (private); development finance.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Development of financial market including development finance (blended finance, conditional loans) provides capital for new green investment. Financial interconnectedness increases. 2. Poor standardization of green investments increases risk of greenwashing, mispricing and conditions for systemic risk. 3. From GDP growth to human well-being: educational and health investments, Green Deal (public spending) expand green economy and opportunities for financialization and financial market development. 4. Cross-country support (e.g. development finance) helps to reduce between countries’ inequality.
SSP2. Middle of the road	Green subsidies; greening monetary policy, conditional	The financial system behaves on a business as usual: high exposures to carbon intensive assets/low exposure

	lending and macroprudential policy (public); as above (private).	to low-carbon assets, high financial actors' interconnectedness; polarization (increase in climate change-driven inequality).
SSP3. Regional rivalry	Local carbon tax and carbon pricing, support for national heavy industry (public); financial sector directly supports gov., households, firms' debt (private).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If finance follows politics: domestic and national focus leads to lower external exposures (financial de-globalisation) decreasing diversification and increasing financial risk. 2. If finance doesn't follow politics: growing divide in performance of the economy/finance. 3. Investments focus on resource and carbon intensive industries, leaving education, technology, climate investments aside.
SSP4. Inequality	Revision of capital requirements for green/brown investments (public North); development finance for energy investments (public South).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Investment trends differ widely across the globe. 2. Finance widens gaps by limiting credit access for some social groups and increasing wealth concentration via financial markets. 3. No financial support to "green growth" (i.e. green investments), development finance support to energy investments only.
SSP5. Highway	No greening of fiscal/monetary policy, support for healthcare and education (public); heavy investment in CCS and fossil fuel companies, no portfolio greening (private).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Later yet larger risk of carbon stranded assets. 2. Difficulty to price risk of fossil and CCS technology in financial contracts/securities increases uncertainty for investors and regulators, and moral hazards. 3. Increase in global markets' integration and interconnectedness creates conditions for risk amplification and cascading systemic risk.

Table 2: Integrating finance into SSPs: challenges and opportunities ahead (based on Battiston, Bressan & Monasterolo in review). Source: Carter et al. (2020).

CMIP5 projections	CMIP6 GCMs	SSP		Sustainability	Middle of the Road	Regional rivalry	Inequality	Fossil-fuelled development
		RCP	W/m ²					
$\Delta T_{2081-2100}^*$	<i>n</i>			SSP1	SSP2	SSP3	SSP4	SSP5
3.2-5.4°C	28	8.5‡						Tier 2
Not evaluated	24	7.0‡			Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2
2.0-3.7°C	7	6.0‡	Tier 2		Tier 1	Tier 1	Tier 2	Tier 1
1.7-3.3°C	26	4.5	Tier 3		Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3
Not evaluated	7	3.4	Tier 3		Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3	Tier 3
0.9-2.3°C	26	2.6‡	Tier 2		Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 2	Tier 1
Not evaluated	10	1.9	Tier 3		Tier 3			

* Global mean temperature change wrt 1850-1900 (includes 0.6°C observed warming to 1986-2005 – IPCC, 2013)

SSP = Shared Socioeconomic Pathway

RCP = Representative Concentration Pathway

 = Unachievable forcing by 2100

 = CMIP5 RCPs

‡ = RCP-based climate projections for which ISIMIP impact simulations are available or planned

Figure 3: SSP-RCP combination and prioritization for the CASCADES project. Note that, in this context, “Tier 1” refers to the prioritization of groups of scenarios as described in Carter et al. (2020) and should not be confused with “Tier 1 Capital (CET1)” mentioned elsewhere for banks. Source: Carter et al. (2020).

Our choice of scenarios does not cover all the scenarios that should preferably be prioritized by all the work packages within the CASCADES project (i.e. “Tier 1” group of scenarios, see Figure 3 and Carter et al., 2020). From that group of scenarios, we only consider SSP2-RCP6.0. In fact, our choice of scenarios is largely impacted by modelling reasons. The initial idea was to apply the macroeconomic shock data obtained from the CASCADES project WP3 (see CASCADES project deliverable D3.4, Delpiazzi et al., 2021). However, the ICES macroeconomic model applied in WP3 considers only climate change impacts on agriculture and energy demand, and, thus, provides very low magnitude of sectoral output shocks for sectors that are not related to agriculture. The application of such shocks in equity valuation model would not produce economically meaningful results, and, thus, would provide a distorted picture of financial markets' impacts from climate change. Instead, the version of the ICES model applied within the COACCH project considers nine different climate change impacts (i.e. climate change impacts on agriculture, forestry, fisheries, sea-level rise, riverine floods, transport, energy supply and energy demand, and labour productivity), and nine combinations of SSPs and RCPs scenarios (Bosello et al., 2020). In this deliverable, we use the four combinations of scenarios that are proposed in the scenarios' matrix of the CASCADES project deliverable 2.1 (see Figure 3 and Carter et al., 2020). For further information regarding the selection of the macroeconomic model, please consult Subsection 4.3.

The four scenarios considered are part of the first (i.e. “Tier 1”, as labelled in Figure 3: SSP2-RCP6.0), the second (i.e. “Tier 2”, as labelled in Figure 3: SSP3-RCP2.6), and the third (i.e. “Tier 3”, as labelled in Figure 3: SSP3-RCP4.5, SSP5-RCP4.5) group of scenarios. The choice of scenarios enables a comparison across different socioeconomic developments, given a specific climate scenario, and across different climate developments, given a specific socioeconomic scenario. This choice reflects a wide range of both climatic and socioeconomic conditions: RCP2.6, RCP4.5 and RCP6.0 for climate and SSP2, SSP3 and SSP5 for socioeconomic conditions. For instance, by including both SSP3-RCP4.5 and SSP5-RCP4.5, we contrast SSPs with a low (SSP3) and a high (SSP5) degree of international connectivity, while considering medium radiative forcing (RCP4.5).

4. Model

4.1 Methodological framework

We apply the methodology introduced in Bressan et al. (2022) which is modular and described in Figure 4. The first block from the left is the database model and data collection, followed by the probabilistic risk assessment approach aimed to translate acute risks into asset-level impacts. We use the CLIMADA model³² for the probabilistic climate risk assessment (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Bresch and Aznar-Siguan, 2021; Geiger et al., 2021; Kropf et al., 2022; Meiler et al., 2022; Mühlhofer et al., 2022; Ortner et al., 2022). Then, in order to quantify chronic risk, we use combinations of SSPs-RCPs scenarios used by the macroeconomic model ICES (Bosello et al., 2020; Eboli et al., 2010; Parrado and De Cian, 2014). Sector level shocks are computed both in absence (“baseline scenario”) and in presence (“impact scenario”) of chronic impacts from climate change. Thus, we quantify chronic shocks on economic sectors by comparing the outcomes of the two scenarios. Subsequently, we combine acute risks on assets and chronic risks on sectors to obtain a shock on equity securities of companies held by European financial actors. We use climate acute and chronic impacts on assets and sectors to adjust the financial valuation of the equity shares of firms that own the assets hit by climate risks, by developing a Climate Discount Dividend Model. Then, we integrate the climate-adjusted financial valuation of stocks into the assessment of the risk metrics of European investors’ portfolios. We denote the direct losses on equity portfolios as “first-round shocks” for banks. Subsequently, the first-round shocks on equity are reverberated through the European financial network using a network model of interbank financial contagion, in order to assess the potential contagion effects among banks. We denote the additional shocks resulting from network amplification as “second-round shocks”. The workflow is illustrated in Figure 4 below.

³² https://github.com/CLIMADA-project/climada_python

Figure 4: Methodological framework of the asset-level approach to climate physical risk assessment and financial valuation. From left to right, the blocks represent consequential steps of implementation. We start from asset-level data collection and harmonization, and then we feed a plant-level probabilistic risk assessment for tropical cyclones. Then, we compute the sector based and macroeconomic impacts of physical risk using the ICES macroeconomic model. By combining climate impacts at asset level and the resulting macroeconomic impacts, it is possible to quantify the climate financial impacts at the company level. Finally, we adjust the financial valuation for equity contracts of the firm that owns the plants, and the resulting adjustment in financial risk for the investor and the financial system. Source: authors' own elaboration.

4.2 Acute risks

We use the CLIMate ADapt (CLIMADA) model³³ (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Aznar-Siguan et al., 2022; Bresch and Aznar-Siguan, 2021; Geiger et al., 2021; Kropf et al., 2022), at different years (2035, 2040, 2045, 2050). Figure 5 below depicts the workflow for probabilistic risk assessment.

³³ <https://wcr.ethz.ch/research/climada.html>

Impact

- **Direct damages** computed at different return periods and on average
- Info feeds into equity shocks and valuation adjustments

Hazards

- **Tropical cyclones** modeled from IBTrACS augmented with a random track generator and using the Holland (2008) wind-field model
- Other **acute** hazards shall be considered in further studies

Geolocalized assets

- Referenced by **latitude/longitude**
- Defined by asset type (e.g. power plant, mine, etc.)
- Non-financial variables (e.g. capacity, residual life)
- Financial variables (e.g. value)

Figure 5: Workflow of our approach to probabilistic disaster risk assessment for tropical cyclones, covering: (bottom panel) spatially explicit exposures, i.e. assets' geographical distribution and assets' characteristics; (mid panel) historical (and synthetic, not shown) hurricane tracks sourced from the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS) and plotted using CLIMADA; (top panel) expected annual impacts on physical assets. The workflow proceeds from the bottom to top of the figure. For readability, the figures are centred on Mexico. Source: Authors' elaboration on CLIMADA's output figures (Aznar-Siguan and Bresch, 2019; Aznar-Siguan et al., 2022) and data from multiple providers.

We consider historical data on tropical cyclones between 1950 and 2021, provided by the International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS)³⁴, covering all tropical cyclone basins³⁵. We retrieve 5,970 tracks with this procedure. We standardize cyclones' tracks by interpolating wind speeds at half hour time steps. We simulate 30 synthetic tracks for each historical event, including track decay after landfall, for the probabilistic assessment. We remove duplicate hazards in the set to obtain a final dataset of 138,849 cyclones. We then map tracks to a global grid of centroids, i.e. geographical points where we define a wind speed from the track. To derive the global grid, we first generate it at 0.5 degrees latitude/longitude, for a total of 204,043 centroids. For each centroid, we compute the distance from the nearest asset in our database, and remove from the grid centroids with a minimum distance larger than 100 km. This procedure allows for a drastic reduction in the computation time of the problem, as the number of centroids is now reduced to 58,778. Moreover, there is no information loss because the discarded centroids are not close enough to assets to be actively used in the model.

³⁴ <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/international-best-track-archive>

³⁵ North Indian Ocean, South Indian Ocean, Western North Pacific, South Pacific and Australia, Eastern North Pacific, North Atlantic.

We use CLIMADA to perturb the tracks for future climate change impacts for a given RCP scenario and year. The procedure followed in the model is based on the results obtained in Knutson et al. (2015) for RCP 4.5. Changes in tropical cyclones' frequencies and intensities are then obtained by linear interpolation for different RCPs and years. In this study, we use RCP 2.6, 4.5 and 6.0, and years 2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050. The choice of RCPs and years is made to match the set-up of the ICES and CDDM models. For limitations of this procedure, see Aznar-Siguan and Bresch (2019), Aznar-Siguan et al. (2022), Bresch and Aznar-Siguan (2021), and Kropf et al. (2022).

By combining the wind speed at the centroid closest to a given asset and a damage function, we obtain asset-level impacts. The damage function describes the relation between the wind speed and the damages to a given asset. Equation 1 shows the formulation used (Emanuel, 2011):

$$F_{index} = \frac{v^3}{1 + v^3}, \quad (1)$$

where:

$$v = \frac{\max((W_{spd} - W_{thresh}), 0)}{W_{half} - W_{thresh}}. \quad (2)$$

Equations 1 and 2 enable the translation of wind speed W_{spd} into direct damages to assets described by the fraction of damaged property F_{index} via a cubic power. It also considers a lower bound W_{thresh} of no property damage occurrence and a value W_{half} where half the damage to property occurs.

We use the calibrated damage function from Dunz et al. (2021) to assess tropical cyclone damages to assets. Based on Mexican data, the value W_{half} is set at 253 km/h and the value W_{thresh} at 65km/h. Importantly, the damage function is here kept constant across all asset types, i.e. a mine will suffer the same damages, such as a power plant.

Both model limitations are relevant for the analysis and will be subject of further research. It is particularly important to assess to which degree the uncertainty of each component affects the uncertainty of the financial cascading risk, since the uncertainty propagation is non-trivial. Nevertheless, the simplifying assumptions do not undermine the validity of the model as long as it is applied at a sufficiently large scale to allow for statistical averages.

We use two measures of damage at each scenario-time combination: Expected Annual Impacts (EAI) and 250 years Return Period (RP250). These combine the damage functions and the hazards to obtain measures of average (EAI) or tail (RP250) risks on assets. EAI at exposure location j is computed as:

$$EAI_j = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{ev}} x_{ij} F(E_i), \quad (3)$$

where x_{ij} is the impact at location j for event E_i , $F(E_i)$ is the annual frequency of event E_i , and N_{ev} is the number of (independent) events considered.

For cyclones, the frequency of an event is defined as the occurrence probability of an event of this type in each year. The impact associated with an event can then be assigned the same frequency, or probability of occurring in a year. The return period of an impact is then obtained as the inverse cumulative probability of an impact of a given magnitude or stronger to occur. For example, the probability in each year that one event resulting in an impact equal or larger to the 1-in-50-year impact occurs is 1/50. Importantly, this does neither imply that every 50 years such an event will necessarily occur, nor that two events of this type cannot happen two years in a row.

For more details on the estimation of return periods see Emanuel and Jagger (2010). For the implementation in CLIMADA, the reader is referred to Aznar-Siguan and Bresch (2019) and the model documentation³⁶.

4.3 Chronic risks

The initial idea was to use the macroeconomic ICES model³⁷ (Delpiazzi et al., 2021; Eboli et al., 2010; Parrado and De Cian, 2014) sectoral output shocks data obtained from the CASCADDES project WP3 (see CASCADDES project deliverable D3.4, Delpiazzi et al., 2021) as chronic climate physical risk shocks for equity valuation. However, we decided to use chronic risk shocks obtained from a different application of the macroeconomic ICES model, namely the H2020 COACCH project³⁸ (see COACCH project deliverable D2.7, Bosello et al., 2020). Both versions of the ICES model were run by CMCC³⁹. The decision to replace the macroeconomic model used to obtain chronic climate physical risk shocks was made after a thorough discussion within the CASCADDES project Consortium. The rationale for such decision is of modelling nature.

The ICES macroeconomic model employed within the CASCADDES project (Delpiazzi et al., 2021) considers only climate change impacts on agriculture and energy demand. Therefore, the sectoral output shocks across scenarios and years are usually low in magnitude. On the other hand, the version of the ICES model employed within the COACCH project includes a wider set of impacts and scenarios. It includes climate change impacts on agriculture, forestry, fisheries, sea-level rise, riverine floods, transport, energy supply and energy demand, and labour productivity. Given a limited number of climate change impacts considered, the usage of macroeconomic shocks obtained from the ICES model within the CASCADDES project would make it difficult or even impossible to translate the sector shocks into shocks on equity and obtain relevant results in terms of financial risk.

³⁶ <https://climada-python.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

³⁷ <https://www.icesmodel.org/>

³⁸ COACCH project received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776479 (<https://www.coacch.eu/>).

³⁹ Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC, <https://www.cmcc.it/>).

There are two reasons for the limited transmission of climate change impacts on agriculture to the financial sector. First, the effects from climate change on the agricultural sector are often positive, due to the CO₂ fertilization effect. Accordingly, there are world regions where agricultural production increases with the worsening of climate change. Although changes in crop yields obtained from the ICES model within the CASCADES project are heterogeneous across crops and regions, for many crops, the average reaction is positive. For instance, the reaction of 'rice' to climate change peaks in Turkey (18% increase) in RCP2.6 in 2070, and the one of 'other grains' peaks in Australia (35% increase) in RCP6.0 in 2070 (for further details about the results of the ICES model simulation, please refer to Delpiazzi et al., 2021). Furthermore, positive effects on agricultural production may, in turn, also induce a positive reaction in output of other sectors.

Second, even when the supply-side effects from climate change on agricultural commodities are negative, the impacts on the country and macro-regional sectoral output and overall GDP level are rather small because of a relatively low share of total value added of the agricultural sector. The contribution of agriculture to total value added in East Asia, excluding high-income countries, is around 8.4%, and in the EU, it amounts to only 1.6%⁴⁰. For example, absolute GDP percentage changes due to agriculture impacts from climate change obtained from the ICES model in the CASCADES project WP3 are, on average, lower than 0.6% of the baseline GDP, across years, scenarios and geographic regions. The effects tend to be larger for higher RCPs and increase over time. In 2030, they range between around -0.26% in Transition Economies and 0.16% in Sub-Saharan Africa in SSP2-RCP6.0. In 2050, GDP effects are more pronounced, and range between around -0.35% in the region "Rest of Asia" and 0.28% in Argentina, in SSP2-RCP6.0 and SSP3-RCP6.0 respectively. In addition, the financial sector is not strongly affected by the agricultural sector shocks because financial actors are not exposed to agricultural companies to an extent high enough to be meaningful for financial valuation of securities held in investors' portfolios. This can be explained by the fact that agricultural companies are usually privately owned, small and medium enterprises (SME), and, thus, not well represented in public equity portfolios of financial actors. Agriculture, forestry and fishing companies account for less than 0.11% of the total equity holdings value in our equity holdings dataset.

Therefore, we decided to replace the scenarios provided by the CASCADES project WP3, with the scenarios used in the COACCH project (Bosello et al., 2020). The sectoral and regional resolution of the model has been adapted to the one used within the CASCADES project deliverable D3.4 (Delpiazzi et al., 2021). Given that the agricultural and energy-demand shocks are two of the multiple climate change impacts that have been included in the COACCH project version of the ICES macroeconomic model, the compatibility of results is ensured. We source GDP and sectoral output trajectories under different combinations of SSPs and RCPs, assumptions of capital mobility and level of climate change impact. Trajectories are provided as "baselines", i.e. without climate change, and as "impact scenarios", i.e.

⁴⁰ Data for 2020, World Bank Indicators available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.AGR.TOTL.ZS>.

including climate change. Thus, the output change from a baseline to an impact scenario is dependent on climate change only. We use the same SSP-RCP combinations listed above, at the time horizons 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050: SSP2-RCP2.6, SSP3-RCP2.6, SSP3-RCP4.5, SSP5-RCP4.5. We use the assumptions of “high” climate impacts and “high” capital mobility, since GDP and sectoral output shocks are more pronounced in these scenarios. GDP changes due to combined impacts from climate change range between -31.96% and 0% across years, scenarios and geographic regions. In 2040, the GDP loss is most pronounced in Indonesia under SSP5-RCP4.5 and amounts to 9.2% from baseline. In 2050, the largest GDP loss is suffered in Japan under SSP2-RCP6.0 and amounts to 12.22% from baseline.

4.4 Climate financial valuation

We assess climate physical risk impacts on equity valuation by developing a Climate Dividend Discount Model (CDDM). It extends the traditional Dividend Discount Model (DDM) framework (Gordon and Shapiro, 1956; Gordon, 1959) in its three stages formulation (Sharpe et al., 1999), to account for acute and chronic shocks on companies’ long-term growth. The former depends on assets and extreme events, the latter on the unique business line assigned to a company and its output trajectory. To estimate the market value of equity, DDMs discount the future dividends using a discount rate to determine their present value. The discount rate represents the rate of return requested by investors. Alternative formulations of this discounting concept exist, for example based on Discounted Cash Flow (DCF). Importantly, our methodology can be applied to DCFs too. We assume the following: (i) dividends can be estimated combining Earnings Per Share (EPS), their growth, payout ratios, and the respective long-run trends; (ii) long-term climate physical risks are not fully reflected in the market (Giglio et al., 2021), thus, the long-run growth rate used for evaluation is not consistent with future climate risks; (iii) long-term growth rate without climate impacts is constant across all companies; (iv) physical risks are going to impact mostly the long-run part of the evaluation; and (v) discount rate is constant for all companies, in all periods.

The model is described by:

$$V_0 = \sum_{t=1}^{t_1} \frac{D_t}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=t_1+1}^{t_2} \frac{D_t}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{V_{t_2}}{(1+r)^{t_2}}, \quad (4)$$

where D_t represents the dividend at time t , r the discount rate⁴¹, and V_{t_2} the terminal value once the explicit estimation of dividends ends. t_1 and t_2 are arbitrary points in time in the future, and it holds $t_1 < t_2$. The following relation connects the dividends to Earnings Per Share (EPS):

$$D_t = EPS_t(1 - b_t), \quad (5)$$

⁴¹ For this study, we set $r = 9.032\%$ consistently with Birman et al (2015).

where EPS_t represents the earning per share at time t , and b_t the earning retention rate, making $(1 - b_t)$ the payout ratio. We obtain EPS and Dividends Per Share (DPS) from S&P. Data are available for a generally limited number of years, thus, to complete the dividend series until t_2 , we first estimate EPS as

$$EPS_t = EPS_{t-1}g_{EPS,t,t-1}, \quad (6)$$

where $g_{EPS,t,t-1}$ represents the EPS growth rate between $t - 1$ and t , and it holds $g_{EPS,t_2} = g_L$, where g_L represents the long-run growth rate of dividends, i.e. the rate at which the company reaches an equilibrium where investment opportunities, on average, earn their opportunity cost of capital. For this study, we set $g_L = 6\%$ consistently with Birman et al. (2015). Importantly, Equation 6 implies a linear decline of EPS growth towards g_L . Thus, Equation 6 allows us to estimate missing EPS, and, hence, dividends from Equation 5. Then, the three stages in Equation 4 can be distinguished as follows. First, a stage where dividends are explicitly estimated by a data provider, S&P for this analysis. Second, a stage where dividends are modelled with linear decline. Third, the estimation of a terminal value.

We can rewrite Equation 4 for each company as

$$V_{0,j} = \sum_{t=1}^{t_{j,1}} \frac{D_t^j}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=t_{j,1}+1}^{t_{j,2}} \frac{D_t^j}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{D_{t_{j,2}}^j (1+g_L)}{(1+r)^{t_{j,2}}(r-g_L)}, \quad (7)$$

The index j represents the j -th company. Differently from Equation 4, we now make the dependence on j explicit, a necessary step for practical applications. In fact, dividend data are generally sourced from a provider whose analysts will perform the in-depth analysis necessary for dividends' estimation. Depending on the company, analysts will use different assumptions while modelling dividends. The usage of company-specific assumptions for the estimation is reflected in the formula by the j subscript, which shows how dividends are going to differ from company to company (denoted D_t^j)⁴², and how the boundaries of the stages are not fixed a priori but depend on the company (denoted by $t_{j,1}$ and $t_{j,2}$). This explicit step is necessary to link the theory of equity valuation to its practical implementation. For a discussion about the sensitivities of the model, please see Bressan et al. (2022). In light of climate change, we cannot keep the long-run growth rate constant across companies, as in Birman et al. (2015), because firms will be heterogeneously impacted. The growth rate of a company will ultimately depend on the output trajectories of its business lines (as impacted by chronic shocks, Subsection 4.3), and the location and characteristics of

⁴² Note that dividends are explicitly modelled in the first stage, up to $t_{j,1}$ and subsequently reverted to long-run growth rates.

its assets (as impacted by acute shocks, Subsection 4.2).⁴³ We can now define the long-run growth rate as adjusted by physical risk considerations, g_L^{44} , as:

$$\widetilde{g}_{L,(I,j)} = g_L \sum_{i=1}^{K_j} \left(\frac{O_{i,I}}{O_{i,B}} \frac{1}{\delta_{j,I,i}} s_i \right), \quad (8)$$

where I denotes a climate change impact scenario, $O_{i,I}$, and $O_{i,B}$ the output trajectories for sector i under scenarios I , impacted by climate change, and B , without climate change. $\delta_{j,I,i}$ represents the company- and business line-specific acute shock under scenario I for sector (business line) i , s_i is the applicable revenue share for business line i , and K_j represents the total number of business lines for company j .

We design $\delta_{j,i}$ as a company- and business line-specific coefficient computed as an average of all $\delta_{a,j,i}$ i.e. the impact coefficient for all physical assets a owned by company j contributing to business line i .

In our application, $\delta_{a,j,i}$ depends on three main parameters for the asset: its monetary value, its residual useful life, and the impact from tropical cyclones computed in CLIMADA.

$$\delta_{a,j,i} = 1 + \eta_a = 1 + \frac{I_{a,j,i}}{V_{a,j,i}} f(R_{a,j,i}), \quad (9)$$

where R_a is the residual life of asset a , $f(R_a)$ a coefficient proportional to the residual life⁴⁵, V_a is the value of asset a , I_a is the acute impact on asset a . Thus, η_a represents an estimate of the impact on assets from tropical cyclones, taking residual life into account. Importantly, we floor δ_j to 1 and cap it to 2, i.e. we assume that companies do not benefit from having physical assets less exposed to climate physical risk, hence simply follow the general sectoral trajectories of their business lines. This assumption is made for simplicity, since assessing the existence of positive effects stemming from asset location requires an analysis which is beyond the scope of the paper. Also, the cap implies that the maximum impact from assets is their destruction.

Note that the estimate of $\delta_{j,I,i}$ is computed on available assets but applied to the full business line. Combining Equations 7 and 8, we obtain the CDDM formulation:

$$\widetilde{V}_{0,I,j} = \sum_{t=1}^{t_{j,1}} \frac{D_t^j}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=t_{j,1}+1}^{t_{j,2}} \frac{D_t^j}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{D_{t_{j,2}}^j (1 + \widetilde{g}_{L,I,j})}{(1+r)^{t_{j,2}} (r - \widetilde{g}_{L,I,j})}, \quad (10)$$

⁴³ Note that dividends are explicitly modelled in the first stage, up to t_j , 1 and subsequently reverted to long-run growth rates.

⁴⁴ Note that, when entering Equation 7, \widetilde{g}_L is always discounted by $(1+r)^{t_2}$, regardless of the considered damage measure for $\delta_{j,I,i}$. This implies that, when considering the RP250 scenario, the discounting for changes in g_L is still $(1+r)^{t_2}$ and not $(1+r)^{250}$.

⁴⁵ For the purpose of this application, $f(R_a) = \frac{1}{\tau} R_a$, where τ equals 1 year.

where $\widetilde{g_{L,I,J}}$ is the adjusted growth rate as per Equation 8 and $\widetilde{V_{0,I,J}}$ is the adjusted valuation. Thus, the combined physical risk shock is given by

$$\psi_j = \frac{\widetilde{V_{0,I,J}} - V_{0,j}}{V_{0,j}}, \quad (11)$$

where $\widetilde{V_{0,I,J}}$ represents the adjusted value under a given impact scenario I . We compute the CDDM under the following scenario combinations: SSP2-RCP6.0, SSP3-RCP2.6, SSP3-RCP4.5, SSP5-RCP4.5. We consider the scenarios in 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050 to compute the corresponding growth rates. Importantly, using a certain year for g_L does not imply extending the dividend stream until that year, but only computing Equation 8 with values for $O_{j,I}$ and $\delta_{j,I,i}$, for that year. We apply full CDDM to all companies with at least two datapoints available for EPS. For stocks paying no dividend, or with no dividend data, we revert to direct shocks, i.e. $\psi_j = \widetilde{g_{L,I,J}} - g_L$. For stocks with data available only for the first period, we compute a one period version of the CDDM following $\widetilde{V_{0,J}} = \frac{D_0}{r - \widetilde{g_{L,I,J}}}$.

4.5 Interbank network model

Finally, we assess the impacts on European financial stability from cascading climate physical risks. To do so, we leverage the NEtwork VALuation (NEVA) model developed in Barucca et al. (2020), and implemented in Roncoroni et al. (2021).

The model enables us to understand the reverberations in the financial network of the mispricing of losses stemming from physical risks. Intuitively, the revaluation of stocks described in the previous section leads to a direct shock on banks' assets, which we label as a "first-round shock". These are losses on assets stemming from direct exposure to companies impacted by physical risks. Subsequently, NEVA enables us to carry out an ex-ante valuation of intra-financial assets as a consequence of the first-round shocks. These "second-round shocks" lead to a devaluation of intra-financial assets and could lead to instability in the banking system. To perform the second-round valuation, the model includes, on top of the climate physical risk shock, an idiosyncratic shock independent from it. The valuation in the model is ex-ante in the sense that the valuation of interbank claims takes place before the maturity of the contract and accounts for some degree of uncertainty on the value of external assets. In this context, external assets are those held by banks that are not invested into obligations from other financial institutions. Interbank assets are banks' investments into other banks. The recovery rate is endogenous in the sense that, in case of default of one or more banks, the valuation of other banks' claims is carried out considering, recursively, the portion of assets' value that banks can recover from their counterparties, depending on their balance sheet (Roncoroni et al., 2021).

The shocks applied in the NEVA model for our study are a combination of:

1. A market conditions scenario, depending on recovery rate and market volatility.

2. A climate physical risk scenario, i.e. a shock emerging from revaluation of equity securities due to the physical risk adjustment, as described in Equation (11) above.

As the valuation for the second shock is supposed to be carried out at the year 2020, the results on financial stability are for the year 2020 as well.

For a description of the contagion dynamics of the model and the novelties, please refer to Roncoroni et al. (2021)⁴⁶.

We first define the market conditions as the set of parameters $\{\sigma, R\}$, where σ captures the magnitude of idiosyncratic shocks on external assets, representing asset price volatility; and R is the interbank recovery rate. For our application, we set $\sigma = 0.5$, and $R = 0.4$. It is also important to notice that, differently to Roncoroni et al. (2021), we do not have information on the structure of the banking network, i.e. confidential data on bilateral interbank exposure. Thus, it is necessary for us to reconstruct the network using total balance sheet quantities, obtained as described in Subsection 2.4. We leverage the same procedure used in Battiston et al. (2017), i.e. the algorithms developed in Cimini et al. (2014, 2015), De Masi et al. (2009) and Musmeci et al. (2013). We need to define two fundamental parameters for this purpose: the number of networks to simulate and the network density. Building on Battiston et al. (2017), we set the density to 20% and simulate 1,000 networks. Then, we run the NEVA model on each network to analyse financial contagion. For the reconstruction of the network and the application of the NEVA model, we match the variables sourced from Orbis to the ones used in Battiston et al. (2017) and Roncoroni et al. (2021)⁴⁷.

The model evolves between time t_0 and time T . Banks are exposed to an idiosyncratic stochastic shock, with uniform support (Roncoroni et al., 2021), at time T . They perform valuation of assets at time t_0 . Intuitively, large enough shocks at time T will lead a bank to default and may impact the stability of its counterparties, as it may lack the means to repay them. Thus, each bank will have a certain probability of default at T , which is taken into account for initial allocation at t_0 .

At time t_1 , with $t_0 < t_1 < T$, the value of external assets is impacted by the unanticipated climate physical risk shock, coming from the re-valuation process described in Section 4.4 and specifically by Equation (11). As discussed, this valuation is dependent on physical risks (both chronic and acute) and conditioned to different climate scenarios. These losses deteriorate banks' equity and thus increase their probability of default.

To derive the value of shocks at t_1 , we first compute the shock for each invested company, as described in Equation (11), for all scenarios listed in Section 3, for both EAI and RP250. Then, we match the shocks on companies with the banks' equity

⁴⁶ Note that investment funds are not used in our application, thus the investment funds related components of the model introduced in Roncoroni et al. (2021) do not apply here.

⁴⁷ The variables correspondence is as follows, described using the convention "Variable network estimation / NEVA -> variable Orbis": Equity -> Equity; Assets -> Total Assets; Interbank (IB) assets -> Loans and advances to banks; Interbank (IB) liabilities -> Deposits from banks + Long term funding; External assets -> Other earning assets.

holdings in our database. For each scenario, we compute the monetary amount of the shock on each equity holding by multiplying the percentage shock (Equation (11)) with the monetary value of the holding. For each bank, we sum the monetary values of shocks on their holdings (computed at the previous step) to obtain the total monetary loss. In this way, we obtain the total amount of losses stemming from equity holdings for each consolidated bank, i.e. the shock at t_1 .

Then, at time t with $t_1 < t < T$, banks carry out a valuation of their interbank claims. For this second round, we build on the methodology and apply the calibration from Roncoroni et al. (2021). Thus, we set the stochastic shock to be uniformly distributed between $[0,1]$. For the advantages and limitations of this assumption, please see Roncoroni et al. (2021). The outcome of the second-round represents the final shock on banks' equity and CET1 capital stemming from physical risks and market conditions, as a result of the network reverberation. This can be expressed as either a monetary value or a percentage of equity and CET1 capital.

We compute the financial network valuation for the final sample of banks described in Subsection 2.4.

5. Results

5.1 Acute vs chronic shocks at the asset and firm level

We apply the methodology to non-EU firms that own plants in our database, and to European investors that own the equity of such firms. Thus, we can capture the cascading effects from non-EU firms to EU investors.

Acute and chronic shocks on firms' assets contribute to shock firms' equity value. In Figure 6, we show the contribution of acute and chronic shocks for 350 companies with available asset-level data. Comparing pairs of companies, four results emerge.

First, companies can suffer large acute shocks even if well diversified, by operating in different sectors (company 1, electricity-renewables vs. company 2, iron & steel). Second, companies may be affected by similar acute shocks but different chronic shocks (company 1, electricity-renewables vs. company 2, iron & steel). Third, companies in the same sector can have similar chronic shocks but very different acute shocks, emerging from asset locations (company 2 vs. company 3, renewables). Fourth, chronic and acute shocks may both contribute to higher combined shocks (company 4, other industries).

Figure 6: Scatter plot showing, for each company (dot), the acute, chronic and combined shocks. Selected scenario: SSP3-RCP4.5, year 2040. Sample size: 350 companies with available asset-level data. X-axis: change in sectoral output from chronic shocks, defined as the loss or gain in sectoral output for a company’s business line. A negative number indicates a loss (e.g. -0.04 indicates a 4% sectoral output loss) and a positive number a gain. Y-axis: acute shock on assets representing the asset-level damages borne by a company, as described by the average of η_a in Equation 9. A higher value represents a higher shock and a value of 0 represents no damages to assets. Colour: combined shock, i.e. final outcome of the full CDDM model. A negative value (darker colour) represents a stronger reduction in valuation. The figure highlights four companies with different business lines, chronic, acute, and combined shocks. The left hand-side box discusses the implications of pairwise comparisons across these highlighted companies.

5.2 Acute shocks lead to large losses on firms’ equity value

Figure 7 illustrates the relation between firms’ losses under EAI and RP250, for the year 2040, regarding 350 companies with available asset-level data. Scenario combinations are shown in different colors and dot styles, respectively SSP2-RCP6.0 (blue cross), SSP3-RCP2.6 (light blue circle), SSP3-RCP4.5 (yellow diamond), SSP5-RCP4.5 (red star). The marginal distributions for EAI and RP250 are represented, respectively, on the bottom and right axis of the chart, approximated as kernel density plots for all scenarios and distinguished by the respective colors. The scatter plot represents the joint distribution. In the figure, losses are represented as negative values, i.e. a value of -0.3 represents a loss of 30% on equity. Conversely, positive values represent gains, i.e. a value of 0.01 represents a 1% increase in equity valuation. While EAI represents average acute shocks, RP250 is characterized by tail shocks. By construction, it holds that the loss under RP250 is always larger than, i.e. more negative, or equal to the one under EAI. This relation holds also in presence of chronic shocks. When the value of chronic shocks is positive, i.e. companies benefit

from chronic climate change, the relation will yield smaller increases in valuation under RP250 than under EAI. This relation is shown by Figure 7, where the dots in the scatter plot are below the black line representing the diagonal labelled *equal shock line* in the figure, where $\text{loss EAI} = \text{loss RP250}$ ⁴⁸. Results are robust to different specifications of the parameters r and g_L (Bressan et al., 2022). Lastly, the two dotted grey lines in Figure 7 represent, respectively, the case of zero change in equity value under EAI (vertical line) and of zero change in equity value under RP250 (horizontal line).

Results across scenarios are stable due to the short time horizon of the analysis (2040). Despite this, some considerations can be made. First, SSP2-RCP6.0 and SSP3-RCP2.6 show more concentration around the mean than SSP5-RCP4.5 and SSP3-RCP4.5. This highlights to some extent the importance of higher RCPs, by comparing SSP3-RCP2.6 and SSP3-RCP4.5. It is likely that this effect is due to the higher tropical cyclones' damages to assets under the higher RCP. Looking at the x-axis (change in equity value under EAI), positive changes under SSP3-RCP2.6 are less pronounced under SSP3-RCP4.5 because of higher chronic risks. Differences in the tail are marginal and difficult to observe. Second, these effects are similarly unclear for the distribution of losses under EAI. In fact, while the distributions under scenarios SSP3-RCP4.5 and SSP2-RCP6.0 are now less dispersed than those under SSP3-RCP2.6 and SSP5-RCP4.5, the difference in the tail is minimal. Third, as a result of the previous considerations, companies tend to experience larger underestimations of losses using EAI for scenarios SSP-RCP4.5 and SSP3-RCP4.5 (due to the higher RCP). Similarly, scenarios with lower acute risks (SSP3-RCP2.6) show lower underestimations of losses. This last point is shown in the scatter plot, where red star signs (SSP5-RCP4.5) and yellow diamonds (SSP3-RCP4.5) tend to lie underneath and to the left of the corresponding light blue circles (SSP3-RCP2.6) and blue cross (SSP2-RCP6.0).

⁴⁸ Deviations from this relation may occur in practice for computational reasons. See Subsection 4.2 for further details.

Figure 7: Scatter plot for the joint EAI and RP250 loss distributions for the year 2040, regarding 350 companies with available asset-level data. Scenario combinations are shown in different colors and dot styles. The marginal distributions for EAI and RP250 are represented, respectively, on the bottom and right axis of the chart, approximated as kernel density plots for all scenarios and distinguished by the respective colors. The scatter plot represents the joint distribution. The loss is defined as $\frac{\widetilde{V}_0 - V_0}{V_0}$, where V_0 is the equity value without the shock and \widetilde{V}_0 is the shocked equity value. The black line labelled *equal shock line* represents the diagonal where the loss under EAI is the same as the shock under RP250, implying no exposure to extreme events. The two dotted grey lines represent, respectively, the case of zero change in equity value under EAI (vertical line) and of zero change in equity value under RP250 (horizontal line). Source: authors' own elaboration.

5.3 Distribution of firms' losses by sectors and countries

Figure 8 and Figure 9 provide an overview of the magnitude of combined shock from acute and chronic climate physical risk components for companies operating in different economic sectors and countries. Figure 8 reports the distribution of changes in equity value by categories for selected sectors, for all scenarios in the year 2040. We consider 350 companies for which physical assets information is available. The horizontal axis in Figure 8 represents sectors. The vertical axis represents categories of changes in equity value for companies, respectively smaller than -25%, between -25% and -15%, between -15% and -10%, between -10% and -5%, between -5% and -2.5%, between -2.5% and -1%, between -1% and 0%, and larger than 0%. In each cell of the heatmap, the number represents the number of companies from the given sector in the given category of changes in equity. For example, for scenario SSP5-RCP4.5 (bottom right), the number 3 in the top-left corner means that 3 companies from the coal sector have an equity shock smaller than -25%. The percentage in parentheses represents the percentage of companies in that cell out of the total of the column, i.e. the sector. For example, for scenario SSP5-RCP4.5 (bottom right), the percentage (13%) in the top-left corner means that the three companies having an equity shock

smaller than -25% represent 13% of all coal companies in the sample. The color represents, within the column, the relative importance of a given cell: a darker color indicates that the cell has a high relative number of companies, while a lighter color indicates that the cell has a low number of companies.

We highlight three important considerations. First, for all scenarios, companies in the 'iron and steel' sector experience the largest losses. Under RP250, around 77% of iron and steel companies experience losses larger than 5% in all the scenarios. The losses in the 'iron and steel' sector are most pronounced in the SSP5-RCP4.5 scenario, because of high chronic shocks and moderate acute shocks in geographic locations where iron and steel manufacturers have production facilities.

Second, companies in the most fossil fuel-driven sector (i.e., companies engaged in coal extraction and production activities) experience the lowest magnitude of losses in all scenarios. In fact, more than 20% of coal companies experience gains in equity valuation in all scenarios. Such result is expected for SSP5, which is characterized by a fossil fuel-driven development of the world. For the remaining scenarios combinations, one important driver is related to CO₂ fertilization effect (Bosello et al., 2020). Accordingly, agricultural production may increase with more climate change. This has also some positive effects on the economy as a whole and, eventually, may lead to positive chronic shocks in economic sectors different from the agricultural one. At the same time, the acute shocks coming from exposure of coal mines to acute risk are quite low. Thus, positive chronic shocks counterbalance the negative acute shocks, leading to a low number of companies which experience negative combined shocks in this sector.

Finally, it is important to note that there are winners and losers among electricity producers. On the one hand, most renewable electricity producers experience losses from combined shocks (i.e. acute and chronic) climate physical risks. In terms of chronic risk, the output in renewable electricity sector decreases in almost all regions, in all scenarios considered. The largest output losses in this sector are in SSP5-RCP4.5 because of intensified use of fossil fuel technologies. The losses from the chronic risk component are complemented by acute physical risk shocks on production facilities of electricity companies, leading to a combined shock ranging from -14% to -31% for more than 70% of companies in this sector. On the other hand, for producers of electricity from fossil fuels, the results are more heterogenous, depending on the scenario and the exposure of the companies' production facilities to acute climate physical risk.

Figure 8: Heatmap showing the distribution of changes in equity value by categories for selected sectors, for all scenarios in the year 2040. Sample size: 350 companies with asset-level data. Horizontal axis: sectors. Vertical axis: categories of changes in equity value for companies. In each cell of the heatmap, the number represents the number of companies from the given sector in the given category of changes in equity. The percentage in parentheses represents the percentage of companies in that cell out of the total of the column, i.e. the sector. The color represents, within the column, the relative importance of a given cell. Source: authors' own elaboration.

Figure 9 reports the distribution of changes in equity value by categories for selected geographical regions, for all scenarios in the year 2040, considering 350 companies for which physical assets information is available. The horizontal axis in Figure 9 represents geographical regions. The vertical axis represents categories of changes in equity value for companies, respectively smaller than -25%, between -25% and -15%, between -15% and -10%, between -10% and -5%, between -5% and -2.5%, between -2.5% and -1%, between -1% and 0%, and larger than 0%. In each cell of the heatmap, the number represents the number of companies from the given geographical region in the given category of changes in equity. For example, for scenario SSP5-RCP4.5 (second from the bottom), the number 3 in the top-left corner means that 3 companies

from Australia have an equity shock smaller than -25%. The percentage in parentheses represents the percentage of companies in that cell out of the total of the column, i.e. the geographical region. For example, for scenario SSP5-RCP4.5 (second from the bottom), the percentage (6%) in the top-left corner means that the three companies having an equity shock smaller than -25% represent 6% of all companies headquartered in Australia in the sample. The color represents, within the column, the relative importance of a given cell: a darker color indicates that the cell has a high relative number of companies, while a lighter color indicates that the cell has a low number of companies.

Although the sign of the shock from the chronic component of climate physical risk is highly dependent on the economic sector in which a given company operates (Figure 8), it is not highly dependent on the geographical region in which a given company is headquartered. On average, the shocks from the chronic risk component are negative in all geographical regions, for all the scenarios considered. The negative chronic shocks are the most pronounced in India, Southeast Asia, as well as in Sub-Saharan and South Africa. The largest negative shocks are experienced for scenario combinations involving stronger climate signal, such as SSP2-RCP6.0. Only in China and Hong Kong (in SSP3-RCP2.6 and SSP5-RCP4.5), the average shock from the chronic risk component is positive. One of the possible explanations for this could be, for instance, the fact that in the fossil fuel-driven world (SSP5), the fossil fuels-related activities in China would experience gains.

Furthermore, no clear relationship emerges between companies' location of headquarters and acute shocks to which the companies are exposed. A reason is the crucial role played by the geographical distribution of companies' productive plants in determining the acute shocks. Thus, companies may suffer impacts on productive assets which are not well proxied by locations of their headquarters.

Combined losses from chronic and acute climate physical risks are the most pronounced in Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. In Taiwan, losses exceed 15% for all the companies considered, while in Japan 80% of companies and in South Korea 86% of companies suffer losses larger than 15%, for all scenarios. This is due to both large chronic and large acute risks, the latter stemming from both domestic assets, which are highly exposed to tropical cyclones, and international assets. In terms of scenarios combinations, irrespective of SSPs, the negative effects from changing patterns in tropical cyclones are more pronounced in higher RCPs, i.e. scenarios combinations with stronger climate change signal. However, due to the short time horizon, variability of results across scenarios is limited.

		SSP3-RCP2.6																			
Change in equity value	EL < -25%	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	11 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (57%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	10 (14%)
	-25% <= EL < -15%	4 (8%)	0 (0%)	7 (7%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	7 (33%)	0 (0%)	12 (60%)	0 (0%)	1 (20%)	3 (43%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	26 (35%)
	-15% <= EL < -10%	4 (8%)	1 (33%)	7 (7%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	4 (19%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (20%)	1 (14%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-10% <= EL < -5%	5 (10%)	2 (67%)	13 (13%)	1 (6%)	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (14%)	1 (10%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-5% <= EL < -2.5%	4 (8%)	0 (0%)	24 (25%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	2 (67%)	1 (20%)	1 (14%)	3 (14%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (11%)
	-2.5% <= EL < -1%	12 (25%)	0 (0%)	6 (6%)	3 (18%)	0 (0%)	5 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	7 (33%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (4%)
	-1% <= EL < 0%	14 (29%)	0 (0%)	27 (28%)	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	5 (24%)	3 (50%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (29%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	2 (67%)	1 (50%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	7 (10%)
	EL > 0%	2 (4%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	9 (12%)
		SSP3-RCP4.5																			
Change in equity value	EL < -25%	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	11 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (57%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (15%)
	-25% <= EL < -15%	4 (8%)	0 (0%)	7 (7%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	6 (29%)	0 (0%)	12 (60%)	0 (0%)	2 (40%)	3 (43%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	26 (35%)
	-15% <= EL < -10%	4 (8%)	1 (33%)	8 (8%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	5 (24%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-10% <= EL < -5%	5 (10%)	2 (67%)	11 (11%)	1 (12%)	1 (100%)	1 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (14%)	1 (10%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (4%)
	-5% <= EL < -2.5%	5 (10%)	0 (0%)	25 (26%)	3 (18%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	2 (67%)	2 (40%)	1 (14%)	5 (24%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (11%)
	-2.5% <= EL < -1%	6 (12%)	0 (0%)	6 (6%)	3 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (24%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (6%)
	-1% <= EL < 0%	19 (40%)	0 (0%)	27 (28%)	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	5 (24%)	3 (50%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (29%)	1 (50%)	1 (50%)	2 (67%)	1 (50%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	7 (10%)
	EL > 0%	2 (4%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (11%)
		SSP5-RCP4.5																			
Change in equity value	EL < -25%	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	11 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (57%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (15%)
	-25% <= EL < -15%	4 (8%)	0 (0%)	7 (7%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	8 (38%)	0 (0%)	12 (60%)	0 (0%)	2 (40%)	3 (43%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	26 (35%)
	-15% <= EL < -10%	4 (8%)	1 (33%)	8 (8%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-10% <= EL < -5%	3 (6%)	2 (67%)	8 (8%)	1 (6%)	1 (100%)	1 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (14%)	1 (19%)	4 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	1 (11%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-5% <= EL < -2.5%	6 (12%)	0 (0%)	25 (26%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	2 (67%)	2 (40%)	1 (14%)	5 (24%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	7 (10%)
	-2.5% <= EL < -1%	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	9 (9%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-1% <= EL < 0%	11 (23%)	0 (0%)	27 (28%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	3 (14%)	3 (50%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (24%)	1 (50%)	1 (50%)	2 (67%)	1 (50%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	12 (17%)
	EL > 0%	14 (29%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (3%)
		SSP2-RCP6.0																			
Change in equity value	EL < -25%	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	10 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (14%)	0 (0%)	4 (20%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (57%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	10 (14%)
	-25% <= EL < -15%	4 (8%)	0 (0%)	8 (8%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	6 (29%)	0 (0%)	12 (60%)	0 (0%)	1 (20%)	3 (43%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (29%)	3 (100%)	0 (0%)	26 (36%)
	-15% <= EL < -10%	4 (8%)	1 (33%)	6 (6%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)	4 (19%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (20%)	1 (14%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	0 (0%)	1 (11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-10% <= EL < -5%	4 (8%)	2 (67%)	8 (8%)	2 (12%)	1 (100%)	1 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (33%)	1 (14%)	1 (14%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (14%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (6%)
	-5% <= EL < -2.5%	5 (10%)	0 (0%)	27 (28%)	3 (18%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)	3 (15%)	2 (67%)	2 (40%)	1 (14%)	6 (29%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	8 (11%)
	-2.5% <= EL < -1%	6 (12%)	0 (0%)	9 (9%)	3 (18%)	0 (0%)	1 (5%)	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (14%)	1 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (7%)
	-1% <= EL < 0%	21 (44%)	0 (0%)	27 (28%)	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	4 (19%)	3 (50%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (29%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)	2 (67%)	1 (50%)	2 (22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	12 (17%)
	EL > 0%	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	2 (2%)	4 (24%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (3%)
		Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	Hongkong	India	Indonesia	Japan	MEKA	Mexico	Russia	Russia	USA							

Figure 9: Heatmap showing the distribution of changes in equity value by categories for selected geographical regions, for all scenarios in the year 2040. Sample size: 350 companies with asset-level data. Horizontal axis: geographical regions. Vertical axis: categories of changes in equity value for companies. In each cell of the heatmap, the number represents the number of companies from the given geographical region in the given category of changes in equity. The percentage in parentheses represents the percentage of companies in that cell out of the total of the column, i.e. the geographical region. The color represents, within the column, the relative importance of a given cell. Source: authors' own elaboration.

5.4 Portfolio tail losses from acute physical shocks

Asset-level climate physical shocks could increase financial risk for investors' portfolios. At the portfolio level, ignoring the tails of acute shocks leads to a large underestimation of losses and financial risk metrics.

Table 3 reports summary statistics for the final sample of 350 companies with asset-level data available. Mean, 95% percentile and 95% Expected Shortfall (ES) are reported under all scenarios for the year 2040, considering both EAI and RP250. To compute the ES, we bootstrap 10,000 equally weighted portfolios of 10 companies and compute the corresponding returns distribution and risk measures. Importantly, the variance across SSP-RCP combinations is relatively small as the valuation is performed with reference year 2040. Larger differences emerge when considering longer time horizons.

Table 3 shows that there are significant differences when risk metrics such as the ES are computed using EAI vs. RP250. In fact, while ES is relatively small under EAI (up to -3%), it is significantly larger under RP250 (up to -14.54%). Thus, considering only EAI would lead to a significant underestimation of risks, as investors would wrongly quantify the ES. This, in turn, can lead to higher-than-expected losses for investors (up to -11.85%).

Statistic	SSP2-RCP6.0	SSP3-RCP2.6	SSP3-RCP4.5	SSP5-RCP4.5
Mean, EAI	-2.57%	-2.64%	-2.62%	-2.39%
Mean, RP250	-9.53%	-9.53%	-9.66%	-9.64%
95% percentile, EAI	-14.61%	-16.28%	-13.19%	-15.81%
95% percentile, RP250	-30.62%	-30.60%	-30.96%	-30.96%
ES, 95%, EAI	-2.53%	-3.00%	-2.98 %	-2.38 %
ES, 95%, RP250	-14.11%	-14.24%	-14.54%	-14.23%
ES difference RP250 – EAI	-11.58%	-11.24%	-11.56%	-11.85%

Table 3: Distribution and portfolio-level results, all scenarios, year 2040. Each row represents the results, for the given statistic, for all scenarios represented in the columns. The mean and 95% percentile are computed over the shock distribution for the 350 companies in the sample where asset-level data are available. To compute the ES, we bootstrap 10,000 equally weighted portfolio and compute the corresponding returns distribution and risk measures. The last row labelled “ES difference RP250 – EAI” shows the difference between the ES95% computed under RP250 and the ES95% computed under EAI. A negative value shows the underestimation of ES stemming from EAI.

5.5 Financial interconnectedness and leverage can amplify climate-related losses

Climate physical shocks lead to losses on the equity value of companies and, consequently, on the portfolios of investors holding their shares. As investors are connected to each other in the financial system, their losses can reverberate and amplify. We focus on the banking system and show how physical shocks can be amplified within it.

In fact, the initial physical shocks on banks, originating from their direct equity holdings in non-financial companies, are contained, but their amplification can lead to larger losses. Similar to previous results, tail acute shocks are larger in magnitude than shocks computed under EAI, and, thus, have a higher relevance for financial stability. For the most impacted banks, the first-round losses can reach only up to -0.05% of their total equity, but the second-round losses, including amplification within the banking system, can account for up to -0.5% losses on total equity (Figure 10, left panel). Importantly, these numbers are higher if we consider CET1 capital instead of total equity. CET1 capital is particularly important for banks because it represents the highest quality capital, as it absorbs losses immediately when they occur. While first-round losses of CET1 capital can reach up to -0.4% for the most impacted banks (Figure 10, right panel), and second-round losses can reach up to -1.8% of CET1.

The losses for banks are contained due to the limited importance of equity investments in their balance sheets. On average, equity investments in non-EU companies represent only 3.09% of banks' total assets. For 6.71% of banks in the sample, equity investments in non-EU companies represent more than 10% of total assets (with a maximum of 72.23%). For 13.42% of banks in the sample, equity investments in non-EU companies represent more than 5% of total assets. Importantly, for 59.06% of banks, equity investments in non-EU companies represent less than 1% of total assets.

As for previous portfolio-level results (see Subsection 5.3), variability across scenarios is limited due to the short time horizon. In fact, no meaningful differences emerge between SSP3-RCP4.5 and SSP5-RCP4.5, neither by computing the first-round loss under EAI nor by computing it under RP250. This emphasizes the importance of considering long-run risks when assessing potential threats to financial stability, in order to properly assess the differences in cascading losses across scenarios.

Thus, financial stability concerns may arise for individual banks due to network amplification of physical losses. Moreover, financial institutions tend to be highly leveraged, i.e. to have small capital compared to total assets. Thus, small losses can trigger systemic financial risk.

Moreover, it is important to consider that these results on financial stability represent a lower bound for multiple reasons. First, the financial system is more complex than the banking system alone. Considering the interactions with insurers, investment funds, and other financial institutions may lead to further amplifications. Second, while we are considering only the European banking system for this analysis, financial

instability may as well be transboundary. As shown by recent crises (e.g. the 2008 financial crisis), shocks on banks in the US or elsewhere can cascade directly on the European financial system. Lastly, we have focused here only on equity investments, which as mentioned represent a small portion of banks' investments.

As coverage of investment portfolios increases (e.g. to loans, bonds, derivatives, real estate, infrastructure, funds, etc.), more shocks could enter the systems and start contagion dynamics.

Similarly, as more climate change risks are considered (both acute and chronic), larger shocks will likely materialize in the financial system.

Figure 10: Largest shocks on total equity (left panel) and on Common Equity Tier 1 (CET1) capital (right panel) for the 6 most impacted banks in the sample. Including both first (red) and second (blue) rounds for a simulated financial network. Vertical axis: banks sorted bottom to top from most impacted to least impacted. Horizontal axis: percentage of shock on equity or CET1. Source: authors' own elaboration.

6. Conclusions

Climate financial risk assessment is crucial to inform investment decisions on climate change mitigation and adaptation, particularly given the interconnectedness and

interdependencies of global financial markets. Standardized disclosure of climate-relevant information is fundamental for risk assessment and for the effective identification of direct and indirect impacts of cascading climate risks in finance. While the importance of climate-related risks has been recognised by investors and regulators, the assessment of cascading climate physical risks in finance is still in its infancy.

In this analysis, we have shown how physical risks can cascade from non-EU companies to the EU banking system. First, we have illustrated the importance of correctly assessing climate physical risks, using asset-level data and considering tail acute risks. We have shown how acute and chronic risks interact to generate shocks on companies' equity and discussed their heterogeneity across firms. Second, we have assessed the underestimation of risk emerging from not considering tail acute risks in financial evaluation. Importantly, not considering tail acute risks can lead to severe underestimation of portfolio risk measures, and thus misallocation of investments in climate adaptation or mitigation. Furthermore, we have shown that the shocks from direct physical risks on equity portfolios can be amplified in the European banking network, potentially leading to meaningful losses on CET1 capital for individual banks. In presence of leverage, this could trigger financial instability. Thus, it is crucial to strengthen the assessment and financial valuation of climate physical risks. Lastly, it is important to notice that little heterogeneity across scenarios can be observed due to the short timeframe of the analysis.

The former point requires improvements in climate-related disclosures and in methodologies used to carry out physical risk assessments. More data need to be available on companies' assets and their business lines, as well as their financial and climate characteristics, to perform a correct assessment. Similarly, more data on financial institutions' exposures to these risks are needed to be able to accurately assess the implications for financial stability. The latter point highlights the need to perform climate risk management for financial institutions and to increase investments in adaptation finance.

Our study is not free from limitations. The main one pertains to data availability, as asset-level and business line-level data are scarce and of limited quality. In particular, the limited number of asset types considered and the assumption of one company being involved in only one business line are crucial limitations which we are working on overcoming. The choice of hazards implies limitations as well, since we are considering only tropical cyclones for acute risks and a limited set of climate impacts for chronic risks in this study. A fully-fledged physical risks assessment would consider also other hazards, such as, for example, floods. Moreover, further limitations apply with regard to the financial instrument considered (equity only) and the contagion dynamics (banks only).

Considering these limitations, the results found in this study have exemplary character and shall be seen as a lower bound for cascading climate physical risks to the European financial system.

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